

Animal Wellness by Means of Tree Plantations

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Limousin cattle in Maremma

Few territories have paid as high a price for historical land-use changes and abandonment as Maremma. Located along the Tyrrhenian coast and bordered inland by the volcanic slopes of Mount Amiata, the Vulsini, Cimini, and Sabatini Hills, Maremma spans Tuscany and Lazio, from the Cecina River in the north to the Tolfa Mountains in the south. During the Roman Empire, the region flourished agriculturally due to efficient water management in coastal salt pans. However, subsequent abandonment led to the creation of extensive marshlands plagued by malaria. It wasn't until the Fascist period and after World War II that significant land reclamation and agrarian reforms took place. Despite these efforts, the area's focus on cereal cultivation and pastoralism simplified the rural landscape, resulting in a vast, treeless expanse of hills and plains. This transformation poses challenges for animal welfare in the region. Livestock farms often depend on hardy cattle breeds like the Maremmana, which are well-suited to free-ranging, or rely on stable-based systems to accommodate more delicate but productive breeds such as Limousin, Charolais, and their crossbreeds with Maremmana. An alternative solution lies in agroforestry, involving tree plantations and the re-establishment of hedgerows to delineate pastures. The success of such efforts depends on selecting locally adapted species and addressing constraints, such as the limited availability of forestry nurseries. Suitable species for hedgerow restoration include *Prunus spinosa*, *P. cerasus*, *Pyrus piraster*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Quercus ilex*, and *Rubus fruticosus*. For sparse tree plantations within pastures or arable lands, Mediterranean species such as *Ceratonia siliqua*, *Pinus pinea*, *P. halepensis*, and *Quercus suber* are viable options. These actions can help rebuild the vital agroforestry matrix at the farm level, restoring balance to the landscape in Maremma.

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